

Impact of Chromium as Industrial Waste on Fish Health of River Ganga in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

The river Ganga is considered sacred and serves as life line for a large number of the population in India. Along with hundreds of millions of peoples, the river basin nurtures a diverse assembly of aquatic including rare and threatened species. These include Dolphins, Otters, ghariyals, crocodiles, fresh water turtles and several species of fresh water fishes. During the last few decades, several anthropogenic activities however have generated huge transformations in the river ecosystem. Rapid urbanization and industrialization contribute heavy pollution to the water. Industrial effluents and sewage entering the river water is one of the prime sources of toxicity, which endangers aquatic biota and deteriorates water quality. In Kanpur alone, tanning, dyeing and paint industries are the major sources of Ganga water pollution. High level of chromium (Cr) has been reported in water because of extensive use of Cr as tanning agent by tanneries. Cr impairs the aquatic environment due to its heavy toxic effects on aquatic life including native fishes. It gets accumulate in the fish's body, causes reproductive and metabolic dysfunction and subsequently transferred to the higher trophic level. Toxicity of Cr in fish leads to severe disturbance in immunological, haematological, biochemical, neurological, enzymatic and reproductive

parameters. In this review article, toxic effects of Cr on freshwater fishes of river Ganga in Kanpur have been discussed.

Key Words: River Ganga, Kanpur, Fish, Tanneries, Industrial waste, Chromium toxicity

Introduction

The River Ganga is revered as sacred in Hinduism, believed to be a Goddess and a source of sin purifier. It serves as a vital lifeline for millions of people in India. In the country, it originates as Bhagirathi River from the Gangotri glacier in Uttarakhand. After merging with the Alaknanda River at Devprayag, Uttarakhand, It becomes the Great Ganges. It is the longest river in India, flowing southeast through northern India and covering approximately 2,525 km through the plains of Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand and West Bengal (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2018). After completing its course In India, the river enters Bangladesh as the Padma River. The Ganga covers nearly 861, 404 km² basin areas in India (approximately 80% of total Ganga basin); the rest lies in Nepal, China and Bangladesh (Gopal B, 2000). The Indo-Gangetic basin covers 29 cities, 97 towns and thousands of villages (Dutta *et al.*, 2020).

Beyond its cultural and spiritual significance, the Ganga River basin supports a rich and diverse aquatic ecosystem, home to several rare and endangered species. These include the Gangetic dolphins, otters, gharials, crocodiles, freshwater turtles, and widely diverse fresh water fish species (belonging approximate 143 species of 11 orders, 72 genera and 32 families- accounting for about 20% of total freshwater fish population found in India) along with critically endangered Ganges Shark (*Glyphis gangeticus*), Gangetic Stingray (*Himantua fluviatilis*), Golden Masheer (*Tor putitora*) and Hilsa (*Tenulosa ilisha*) (Sarkar *et al.*, 2012). Flowing through Kanpur, the River Ganga supports many varieties of fish population, providing an excellent example of biodiversity. River not only serves shelter and nourishment to aquatic life but also provides food and employment to humans. Despite their ecological significance, Fish populations in the city face multiple threats including severe pollution, habitat destruction and degradation, and overfishing, which together contribute to species decline and loss.

The rapid expansion of agriculture and industries in the Indian Sub-continent has placed severe strain on the Ganga River, leading to significant deterioration of its water quality. Contributing factors include the excessive discharge of Industrial effluents, untreated sewage, agricultural runoff, and the disposal of human and animal remains in the river. These activities introduce decayed residues, organic matters and pollutants that cause substantial disturbances in

physicochemical and biological parameters of river water, often exceeding allowable limits (Misra A, 2024). As a result, the water becomes unsuitable for drinking and poses severe threat to aquatic life (Roy and Shamim, 2020). This review article highlights the toxic impact of chromium as industrial waste on the fish health of river Ganga in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Geographical Course of River Ganga In Uttar Pradesh

In the largest state of Northern India- Uttar Pradesh, River Ganga is considered as the most important river as it supports a significant portion in the state's population and economy (Arya and Gupta, 2013). It appears first time in plains at Haridwar, Uttarakhand and enters Uttar Pradesh through Bijnor. River Ganga flow approximate 1140 km. length through 28 districts of Uttar Pradesh (middle stretch- from Narora to Ballia) and then enters Bihar through Ballia. In Uttar Pradesh, the Ganga basin is the largest drainage region, covering about two-third of the state's area. It comprises the Ganga along with numerous tributaries like Yamuna, Ghaghara and Gomati Rivers. This region is known for its fertile plains and is home to some of the most populous cities in the state including Varanasi, Allahabad and Kanpur (Rahaman, 2009).

Fish Diversity In River Ganga At Kanpur

Kanpur, an industrial city situated on the banks of River Ganga, has amassed a diverse collection of freshwater fish species. A total of approximately 74 common species were noticed belonging to 6 orders (Fig.1) in the River Ganga at Kanpur. These include: Cypriniformes (32 species), Siluriformes order (21 species), Perciformes (15 Species) Clupeiformes (3 species). Rest were from Osteoglossiformes (2 species) and Tetraodontiformes (1 Species) (Listed in Table-1). The introduction of exotic species such as *Cyprinus carpio var. communis* and *Oreochromis niloticus* has also reported in this region. These exotic fishes are also found alarming for indigenous species biodiversity, as they are frequent powerful invaders in the River Ganga (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2016).

Fig.1: Percentage composition of Common fish orders inhabiting the River Ganga at Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2016)

Table-1: Common fish species inhabiting the River Ganga at Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2016)

Orders (Major Fish)	Fish Species
Cypriniformes	<i>Catla catla</i> , <i>Chagunius chagunio</i> , <i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i> , <i>Cirrhinus reba</i> , <i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i> , <i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i> , <i>Cyprinus carpio communis</i> , <i>Cyprinus carpio specularis</i> , <i>Aristichthys nibilis</i> , <i>Labeo calbasu</i> , <i>Labeo bata</i> , <i>Labeo boga</i> , <i>Labeo rohita</i> , <i>Osteobrama cotio cotio</i> , <i>Puntius sarana sarana</i> , <i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Puntius ticto</i> , <i>Chela laubuca</i> , <i>Salmostoma bacaila</i> , <i>Salmophasia phulo</i> , <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> , <i>Aspidoparia jaya</i> , <i>Aspidoparia morar</i> , <i>Barilius barila</i> , <i>Barilius bola</i> , <i>Rasbora rasbora</i> , <i>Securicula gora</i> , <i>Crossocheilus latius latius</i> , <i>Nemacheilus botia</i> , <i>Botia lohachata</i> , <i>Botia dario</i> , <i>Lepidocephalus guntea</i>
Siluriformes	<i>Sperata aor</i> , <i>Sperata seenghala</i> , <i>Mystus tengra</i> , <i>Mystus cavasius</i> , <i>Mystus vittatus</i> , <i>Rita rita</i> , <i>Ompak pabda</i> , <i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Ailia coila</i> , <i>Clupisoma garua</i> , <i>Eutropiichthys vacha</i> , <i>Eutropiichthys murius</i> , <i>Silonia silondia</i> , <i>Bagarius bagarius</i> , <i>Gagata cenia</i> , <i>Nangra viridescens</i> , <i>Sisor rhabdophorus</i> , <i>Clarius batrachus</i> , <i>Clarius gariepinus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Xenentodon cancila</i>
Perciformes	<i>Chanda nama</i> , <i>Chanda ranga</i> , <i>Johnius coitor</i> , <i>Rhinimugil corsula</i> , <i>Sicamugil cascasia</i> , <i>Glossogobius giuris</i> , <i>Anabas testudineus</i> , <i>Colisa fasciatus</i> , <i>Channa marulius</i> , <i>Channa punctatus</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Channa stewartii</i> , <i>Macrognathus pancalus</i> , <i>Mastacembelus armatus</i> , <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>
Clupeiformes	<i>Gadusia chapra</i> , <i>Goniolosa manmina</i> , <i>Setipinna phasa</i>
Osteoglossiformes	<i>Chitala chitala</i> , <i>Notopterus notopterus</i>
Tetraodontiformes	<i>Tetradon cutcutia</i>

Chromium- Industrial Waste In River Ganga, Kanpur

Kanpur, the second most populous city of Uttar Pradesh, is also known as the “City of Industries”. It is famous for its strong reputation in producing export-quality leather goods. The city hosts a large number of leather industries, tanneries along with other industries such as fertilizer, detergent, chemical and paint manufacturing. Most of the industries are situated along the banks of River Ganga. They release untreated hazardous waste directly into river Ganga, leading to severe water pollution and posing a serious threat to inhabitants (CPCB Report, 21 July, 2023). According to this report, the industrial area of Kanpur records BOD (Biological Oxygen Demand) level of 4.60 mg per litre in the Ganga at Jajmau. Many of these units discharge various types of waste into the environment, mainly in the form of liquid effluents that contain both organic matter, toxic chemicals and heavy metals such as chromium, cadmium, arsenic, mercury and nickel as well as sulphides, ammonium and other salts, chemical dyes, Sulphuric acid and methane (CPCB, 2023).

Recent reports indicate that tanneries in Uttar Pradesh account for nearly 90% of the state’s industrial pollution, releasing some of the most hazardous effluents into the river Ganga. These pollutants are concentrated along the side areas of the river; The Chromium load in these discharges often exceeds permissible limits multiple times, with approximately 1,125 tons of Chromium being dumped into the river every year.

Kanpur’s long established leather tanning industry discharges massive volume of chromium- rich effluents directly into ground water sources, surface water bodies (pits and ponds), or into the River Ganga. Reported chromium concentrations in the river near Kanpur are approximately 124 times higher than the permissible limit, reaching up to 248 mg/l compared with the safe limit of 2 mg/l (The Indian Express, 2011). Nearly 400 tanneries located in the Jajmau region of Kanpur alone generate around 50 MLD of waste. The rapid growth of tanneries in this region has turned the River Ganga into a dumping Ground. The rapid expansion of tanning, dyeing, and textile manufacturing industries has further intensified the pollution load, with tanneries- relying on chromium (Cr) as a principal processing agent- constituting the most critical source of contamination. Chromium is a highly toxic heavy metal that severely affects aquatic life. Once released into the river, it accumulates in fish tissues, leading to metabolic and reproductive

disorders. This bioaccumulation not only threaten fish populations but also transfers toxicity through the food chain, putting higher trophic levels at risk.

Monitoring of Ganga River from Rishikesh to Varanasi indicated that Kannauj to Kanpur and Varanasi are the most polluted stretches of river Ganga (Singh *et al.*, 2003). The analysis of Upstream and downstream water and sediments revealed chromium concentrations at the Jajmau area at Kanpur to be nearly 10 folds higher, reflecting the unchecked release of untreated tannery effluents (Kawaja *et al.*, 2001). The continuous discharge of untreated industrial effluents along with sewage from the city has resulted in severe pollution of the River Ganga. It is deteriorating the quality of water and aquatic flora (Misra, 2024). Such anthropogenic activity has caused the river to experience a gradual ecological decline in Kanpur. The Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB, 02 Jan, 2017) identified this region as the "most polluted stretch" of the River Ganga, as the industries persistently ignore environmental regulations and fail to comply with green norms.

Impact of Chromium Toxicity On Fish Health

Chromium generally exists in multiple oxidation states, of which Cr (0), Cr (III) and Cr (VI) are the most stable and prevalent forms. Cr (0) is primarily used in the production of steel and alloys. Cr (III), generally present as oxides, hydroxides and sulphates, is relatively less toxic and poorly soluble in water. In contrast, Cr (VI), commonly occurring as chromate, dichromate, or CrO₃, is highly toxic, soluble and mobile. Owing to its strong oxidizing nature, Cr (VI) easily penetrates biological membranes, disperses throughout the environment. Depending on the quantity, duration, and route of exposure, it causes moderate to severe illnesses, significantly affecting the health of living organisms (Misra and Srivastava, 2025).

Chromium bioaccumulation in fish

Chromium is recognized as a well-established heavy metal toxicant, and its presence in aquatic organisms represents a significant global concern. In fish, toxicant enter the bodies through two main pathways- first, via the gills during respiration, where they are quickly absorbed into the blood stream; and second, by consuming contaminated phytoplankton, that have accumulated high concentrations of heavy metal. (Obasohan, 2007). The bioaccumulation of chromium varies across different tissues in fish. High levels of accumulation are typically observed in the gills, liver and kidney, whereas very low concentration is found in the muscle tissue. This element adversely

affects fish health, growth and overall productivity, and exhibit a strong tendency for bioaccumulation within their tissues (Emon *et al.*, 2023).

The extent of chromium bio-accumulation in aquatic environments is influenced by various ecological factors too such age, species and the developmental stage of the organism as well as abiotic conditions like temperature, pH and the presence or absence of dissolved salts. Several studies have documented disruption in hematological, biochemical, neurological and enzymatic activities along with behavioral changes, caused by severe chromium toxicity in fish (Kamila *et al.*, 2023) (Fig.2).

Fig.2: Major disturbances in various biological parameters caused by Chromium toxicity in fish

Numerous symptoms of chromium toxicity have been reported in fishes of River Ganga at Kanpur city, including physical deformities (skin lesions, ulcers, loss of scales on skin, fin rot, abnormal pigmentation, body deformities and bulging eyes). Physiological damage is also evident, as toxicants accumulate in gills, liver, kidneys and muscles, leading to tissue degeneration and organ dysfunction. In addition, reproductive impairment, metabolic disturbance and noticeable behavioral alterations (Summarized in Table-2) such as lethargy, erratic swimming and loss of schooling behavior have been observed (Arya and Shukla, 2018).

Table-2: Summary of the adverse effects of chromium contamination on various freshwater fish species

Effects	Symptoms developed in fish after exposure to chromium	References
Acute effect	<i>Behaviour</i> - Hyperactivity, erratic swimming, loss of body balance, increase rate of mucus secretion	Nisha <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Vutukuru SS, 2003 Virk and Sharma, 2003 Bakshi and Panigrahi, 2018
	<i>Mortality</i> - 96 hrsLC ₅₀ value ranges from 30.36 mg/l – 155.00 mg/l depending on the pH, temperature and quality of water	
	<i>Cellular system</i> - reduced cell viability, significant ROS production, affects growth kinetics of cell, apoptosis	
	<i>Immune responses</i> - Significant antibody suppression, impair immunity	
	<i>Biochemical</i> - elevate levels of certain enzymes i.e. alanine amino transferase, aspartate amino transferase, increase glucose absorption, alter osmoregulatory function by regulating Na ⁺ /K ⁺ conc.	
	<i>Endocrine</i> - Disturbance and strong fluctuation in Thyroid hormones (TSH, T ₃ and T ₄)	
Chronic effect	Physiology- reduce growth rate, hampers survival, alter biochemical mechanisms by lowering the Glycogen content in gills, liver and kidney, inhibit LDH activity in liver and kidney, inhibit pyruvate dehydrogenase and succinate dehydrogenase activities in liver and kidney tissues, impaired glycogenesis, hypoxia	Islam <i>et al.</i> , 2020 Velma <i>et al.</i> , 2009
	Histopathology- Hepatocytic necrosis, Fenestrated glomerular epithelium, degradation in inner intestinal epithelium, Loosening of muscle fibres, High lamellar degradation in gills, thickening of blood vessels, Atrophied central axis of gills.	Kamila <i>et al.</i> , 2023 Selcuk <i>et al.</i> , 2010
	Cellular system- damage cell membrane, decrease in leucocyte counts, reduce haemoglobin concentration, reduce spleenocyte counts i.e. weight loss of spleen	Mishra and Mohanty, 2008
	Immune responses- immunosuppression, decreased antibody responses	
	Enzymatic- inhibit enzymatic activity of succinate dehydrogenase, lactate dehydrogenase, puruvate dehydrogenase, evident hyperglycemia and hyperlactamia observed	
	Endocrine- fluctuation in hormone function, exhibit foetotoxic & embryotoxic effects, alteration in plasma cortisol, TSH, T ₃ and T ₄ hormone level.	

Seasonal variation in heavy metal accumulation was also observed in the gills, skin and muscle tissues of fishes from the River Ganga. The highest concentrations were recorded during the monsoon season, while the lowest levels were found during the pre-monsoon period across all fish species. This pattern may be attributed to increased surface run off during the monsoon, which carries substantial loads of heavy metals such as Chromium from tanneries, dyeing units and metal-processing industries located along the riverbanks (Misra and Srivastava, 2025).

Consumption of contaminated fish facilitates the transfer of heavy metals into the human via food chain, thereby posing substantial public health risks (Krogh and Scanes 1996). Furthermore, heavy metal exposure disrupts key metabolic processes in aquatic flora and fauna, leading to ecological imbalances and impairment of ecosystem functions. In humans, ingestion of heavy metal laden fish has been associated with diverse physiological disorders, including hypertension, sporadic fever, renal damage, muscular cramps and progressive kidney dysfunction (Pani *et al.* 2002).

Conclusion

The increase in organic and inorganic pollution, along with a decrease in the water volume of the River Ganga, has severely impacted fish diversity and health. Areas like Kanpur, which have a high concentration of industries, significantly contribute to water pollution in the River. The continuous discharge of toxic industrial effluents poses a serious threat to both native and migratory fish populations. The stretch of the River Ganga around Kanpur (especially Jajmau) is heavily affected by chromium (an important tanning agent, used in most tanneries) contamination. Due to the chromium contamination, a notable decline of economically important fish species has been recorded and reported by various researchers. Several species of freshwater fish accumulate chromium from contaminated water beyond the permissible limit. The biomagnification of this metal has been reported in various popular fishes of the River Ganga. Toxic element bioaccumulate and magnify in the fishes of Ganga, resulting in a significant exposure pathway and consequent health risk to the fish-consuming human population in Ganga basin. With rapid industrial expansion, Kanpur has consistently failed to manage and mitigate the growing burden of industrial pollution. These findings underscore the urgent need for stricter pollution control laws, public awareness, health-based consumption guidelines and greater emphasis on sustainable environmental management to protect this invaluable ecosystem.

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